

THE ROLE OF CUSTOMS PAYMENTS IN THE FORMATION OF THE STATE BUDGET

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Every country strives continuously to strengthen its production capacity in order to secure a stable position in the global market. In this process, analyzing and optimizing the composition of imports, as well as enhancing export potential, are of vital importance for successful entry into foreign markets and improving competitiveness. The liberalization of foreign trade serves precisely these objectives.

Customs payments play a crucial role in regulating foreign economic activity by shaping an efficient structure of foreign trade, protecting domestic producers from unfair foreign competition, and ensuring revenue inflow to the state budget.

The collection of Customs payments is considered one of the essential conditions for the clearance of goods transported through the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Proper and accurate application of these duties ensures revenue inflow to the state budget, which positively contributes to the sustainable development of the economy.

Based on the above, it is one of the urgent issues today to theoretically study the application of Customs payments in regulating foreign trade, utilize the theoretical conclusions drawn to make sound decisions in practice, particularly in replenishing the state budget, and to research and improve the mechanisms for collecting Customs payments, as well as develop conclusions and recommendations.

World scholars have provided various definitions regarding the essence and theoretical foundations of Customs payments and their application. In particular, V.Yu. Zhukoves defines Customs payments as the total amount of all mandatory payments that an individual must pay to customs authorities when transporting goods across the customs border of the customs union [1].

O.Yu. Bakayeva defines Customs payments as mandatory payments collected by customs authorities in accordance with established procedures, which include taxes and non-tax revenues paid during the transportation of

goods across the customs border of the customs union and serve the function of taxes payable to the budget [2].

V.G. Svinukhova, in his two scientific works, provides two entirely different definitions of the term "Customs payments." In one research study, he defines Customs payments as compulsory payments collected by customs authorities during the import or export of goods, which are a necessary condition for the import or export of goods. In another work, he describes Customs payments as taxes and fees collected by customs authorities directly related to the movement of goods across customs borders. At the same time, he emphasizes that the payment of these duties is an essential condition for the application of customs procedures [3].

According to the Uzbek economist T.N. Pardayev, Customs payments are payments collected for goods and material assets transported across the customs border, which constitute a part of the revenue of the state budget [5]. Currently, the composition of Customs payments in the Republic of Uzbekistan includes customs tariffs, excise taxes, value-added tax, customs fees, and other customs payments.

The share of Customs payments in the revenue part of the state budget has been steadily increasing year by year. While this indicator was 18.2% in 2014, it reached 25.2% by 2023, reflecting a growth of 5.0% during this period (Table 1).

In addition to customs fees, Customs payments account for 100% of the revenue portion of the state budget.

Table 1.

Share of Customs payments in the Revenue Portion of the State Budget (in percentage)

№	Indicator	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
11	Share of Customs payments in the Revenue Portion of the State Budget, %	18,2	16,8	13,8	15,3	14,5	15,3	18,5	20,1	22,8	25,2

Source: Prepared by the author based on data from the Customs Committee.

In the Russian Federation, revenue from Customs payments accounts for 50% of the state budget's income. This indicator varies among countries worldwide and depends on the level of development of the state and its position in the international division of labor. In developing countries, the high volume of raw material exports and significant external debts often necessitate increased customs duty revenues to the budget. In developed countries, revenues from Customs payments make up approximately 12-20% of the budget [4].

Amid the intensifying process of economic globalization worldwide, it is essential for a country to achieve sustainable growth in foreign trade and enhance its positive impact on the economy by continuously improving foreign economic activities in accordance with trends and changes in the global market.

Since gaining independence, Uzbekistan has acquired the ability to conduct an independent foreign economic policy aligned with national interests. In this context, managing foreign economic activities involves key objectives such as ensuring stable economic development, transitioning to a socially-oriented market economy, and fostering international integration processes while taking into account the increasing global interconnectedness.

In recent years, comprehensive reforms have been implemented in the areas of calculating, collecting, and directing Customs payments to the state budget. At the same time, the regulatory and legal framework governing these areas is being systematically improved.

As a result of creating favorable conditions for participants in foreign economic activities, the amount of Customs payments collected has been increasing year by year. Analysis shows that this figure has increased tenfold between 2014 and 2023 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The amount of Customs payments transferred to the State Budget by the customs authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan during 2014–2023 (in billion soums).

Source: Prepared by the author based on data from the Customs Committee.

Several key factors have contributed to the increase in Customs payments, including the rise in the volume of imported goods, improvements in the determination of the customs value of goods, changes in customs duty rates,

fluctuations in the exchange rate of freely convertible currencies, the effective use of automated information systems in the customs sector, and the ongoing enhancement of the regulatory and legal framework in the field of customs.

According to the results for the year 2023, the composition of total customs payments in the Republic of Uzbekistan was as follows: value-added tax accounted for 80.0% of total payments, import customs duty made up 16.0%, excise tax constituted 0.1%, and other types of payments represented 3.9%. For comparison, in 2019, these figures were 78.5%, 13.5%, 4.6%, and 3.4%, respectively (see Table 2).

Table 2.

The Composition of Customs Payments Transferred to the State Budget by Customs Authorities in 2019–2023 (in percentages)

№	Types of Customs Payments	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Import Customs Duty	13,5	14,3	14,0		
2	Value-Added Tax (VAT)	78,5	79,8	82,0		
3	Excise Tax	4,6	3,7	1,0		
4	Customs Fees and Other Payments	3,4	2,2	3,0		
Total		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0

Source: Prepared by the author based on data from the Customs Committee.

Based on the above analysis, the following measures are recommended to enhance the role of customs payments in the formation of the state budget:

introduce export duties for certain key goods exported from the country;

conduct systematic analysis of the factors affecting the collection of customs payments;

improve the mechanism for calculating and collecting customs fees in accordance with international standards.

In conclusion, the effective application of customs payments contributes to the development of the national economy, the expansion of foreign trade volume, and the sustainability of the state budget.

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